

OCCURRENCE OF SYNTAGMATIC RELATIONSHIP IN SPEECH

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Annotation: In this article, thoughts are expressed about the concept of relation, in particular, syntagmatic relation, and an attempt is made to reveal the possibilities of syntagmatic relation with the help of excerpts from works of art.

Key words: relationship, syntagmatic relationship, types of syntagmatic relationship.

Today, as in every field, education, especially language education, is developing and growing rapidly. Linguistics is moving away from traditionalism and moving towards non-traditionalism. Many new scientific works and dissertations are being created, including this article. The topic is one of those news. The article also reveals the possibilities of syntagmatic communication. Before we dwell on the concept of syntagmatic relationship, let's talk about the concept of relationship itself.

About the concept of "attitude". In philosophy, relation is considered as the nature of arrangement of elements in a certain system and their interrelationship. For example, a person lives in relation to other people in society. This connection is the attitude of the person. The relationship between family members can be a clear proof of this. In the family, the special relations between father and mother, between them and their children, and between children show the characteristics of the family system. Each member (element) has a place in it.

Literature review

The sequential relationship of a specific syntactic unit with another syntactic unit creates a syntagmatic relationship. Since a syntactic unit is a whole consisting of a unity of form and content as a high-level unit in the structure of the language system, the syntagmatic relationship between syntactic units also has a dual nature:

- a) formal syntagmatic relation;
- b) syntagmatic relation of content.

Formal syntagmatic relationship. The sequential relationship of a certain syntactic form (the form of a sentence) with another syntagmatic form is considered a formal syntagmatic relationship. In traditional linguistics, the terms "syntactic relationship" and "syntactic communication" are distinguished.

The term "syntactic relationship" refers to the substantive syntagmatic relationship between syntactic units, and the term syntactic relationship refers

to the expressive side of the formal syntagmatic relationship. Any formal syntagmatic relationship represents a certain meaningful syntagmatic relationship, and these two relationship units reflect the dialectic of form and content. For example, the syntactic device "I came" consisting of the formal relation of the possessor and participle expresses the substantive relation of the subject and the predicate.

Research methodology and empirical analysis

As the syntagmatic relationship enters into a formal and meaningful relationship, it occurs in the speech as follows:

The rain pattered on the window,
From the trail we left yesterday.
Mists engulfed the ruined gardens,
My love, what happened to you?¹

If we look at the syntagmatic connection of the words "disappeared gardens" and "conquering fog" in these verses, the word "disappeared" is used in relation to the mental state of a person. In this syntagmatic unit, it is combined with the word garden. In this case, the lexeme "parishon" was used in the poem in order to further strengthen and exaggerate the silence of the gardens, because the word "parishon" contains the symbols of silence and silence. It is not correct in terms of content because of its lack of meaning. The garden left in the district is described as "the district won". In this combination, it is emphasized that the fog is very thick and the garden is not noticeable in this fog.

Just don't look at me like that
The moon that broke my eye.²

In the above verses, the condition of the moon when it has just risen is compared to the breaking due to "eye contact" and "gazing". In fact, the moon does not break, but artistically, in a metonymic state, the new moon is likened to a "broken moon" and enters into a syntagmatic relationship.

Is the world sick... my days are sad,
Dilgir Khazans fall.

The above situation also occurred in the unit of "dilgir hazans" in these verses. Since the falling of khazons on the head seems like a close person stroking and encouraging the head, the lyrical hero describes the khazans as "happy". In fact, the khazans cannot be happy. When autumn comes, due to the natural

¹Zebo Mirzo.Ishq. Toshkent,2011. 156-b

²Behzod Fazliddin.Kutmagan kunlarim,kutgan kunlarim. Toshkent,2009. 276-b

phenomenon of nature, the trees lose their leaves. They will eat and drink. But the internal treasury scheme in the spilling of khazans has come to the fore.

As the light falls on the bosom of the garden,
Happiness blooms on the branches.

In the above verses, the flowering of trees is compared to the flowering of HAPPINESS. In fact, happiness does not bloom, but we can witness that the associative themes of rejuvenation, joy, and blossoming in the word happiness have occurred.

Syntagmatic relationship is a very broad concept. Syntagmatic relationship is not only the relationship of neighborhood, but also the proportionality of meanings. In the syntagmatic relationship, in the process of combining words with each other, their internal associative meanings are also revealed and realized.

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